

COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF STUDENT'S CLASSROOM INTERACTIONS

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Abstract

The objective of this research are to explore the learners' use of communication strategies when they interact orally in English in classroom context; to find out learners' intercultural communicative competence (ICC) in terms of English listening and reading skill and intercultural competence. This research methodise qualitative approach which describes the real performance of communication strategies use, background and reasons underlying the employment and the impact on learners' motivation to speak and participate in speaking activities in the classroom. The number of participant in this research is 25 of 56 student's population The respondents are randomly selected without considering the gender and proficiency at preliminary stage. The age ranged from 20 to 23 years old to represent adult learners of English. Based on the results of observation, it is found that there are 14 communication strategies of taxonomy used by respondents, two strategies are used by 10 respondents each, namely self-repetition and code switching strategies. Meanwhile, the most frequently used strategy is use of filler which is employed only by 8 respondents. Based on the results of data analysis, it is found that some communication strategies are employed more frequently than those of the other strategies which lay on the employment of "use of all purposes words" and "foreignzing" strategies that are found in the current study only. Furthermore, these researches find that "self-repetition" strategy is the most popular strategy to use.

Keywords: Communication strategies, intercultural communicative competence, willingness to communicate.

Introduction

Speaking on a daily use is a tool to of communication to express our opinions, and to project an image of who we are. Speaking skills are now a major component in most international and local language examinations, as they are recognized as essential for international mobility, entrance to higher education, and employment (Fulcher, 2015; Isaacs, 2016). This is at least partially due to the rise of the communicative movement in language teaching and assessment. In today's globalized world, speaking skills are recognized as essential for international mobility, entrance to higher education, and employment (Fulcher, 2015; Isaacs, 2016; Fulcher, 2000).

The growing challenges of society today encourage foreign language learning to respond better to a changing world. It is urgent to respond appropriately to the developing needs in the 21st century, otherwise the education cannot fulfil students' need in preparing them for effective functioning in the modern world. Erdogan (2019) emerged an idea to integrate the four skills of the 21st century (communication, collaboration, creativity and critical thinking skills) into language skills in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classes which then it deduced that foreign language learning should be focused on developing communication skills which was closely related to collaborative skills in which collaboration was a key factor to connect to today's global society.

The study reported that students' major academic oral communication difficulties were limited accurate speaking, problems in communicating ideas fluently, less clear pronunciation speaking, and lack of confidence when communicating ideas (Toro, et. al., 2018). Many Indonesian learners suffered anxiety when they were facing with speaking English that made them too much worry and fear during the preparation and delivery of talks (Kurniawati& Putri, 2021; Solikhi, 2021) which certainly impeded fluency development. The complaint was sounded harder when it dealt with non-English learner who considered English not as main subject to learn although it was compulsory.

Referring to speaking problems faced by Indonesian learners, Andas&Rutniatyanti (2020) found four problems namely inhibition, lacking of ideas, low or uneven participation in class, and low motivation. The role of environment to encourage learning success was also mentioned by Park &Schlight (2021) who stated that learning English was reinforced when English learners, especially the ones of non-native speakers of English, had freedom and interactive support from society besides careful scaffolding to make them confident, proficient, and Basic English user.

Responding to the problem of EFL learners' low ability to speak, this study is aimed to discover solution where the research was be based on the theory of "communicative competence". This was the underlying theory of communicative language teaching (CLT) and communicative competence (CC) concept (Byram, 1997). Basalama (2018) and Pham & Pham (2022) supported that attachment of CC in foreign language learning would bring benefits to speaking skills development which in turn increased communication among people across nations.

Using the same basis of theory which had been developed by Canalé& Swain (1980) in analysing the problems, lack of speaking skills development might be caused by deficiency of one or more competences which comprises the communicative competence. Meanwhile, acquiring knowledge of sentences is not sufficient to make a child communicate in a given social-cultural set up (Bern, 1990). Therefore, those complaints on speaking skills development were due to shortage of one or more elements of communicative competence.

In spirit to solve the problems of speaking skills development, special attention was given to "strategic competence" which was expected to facilitate resolving them. This is an element of communicative competence which has a specific role in solving the communication breakdowns because it provides the speakers or the learners ways to use the language strategically (Canalé& Swain, 1980), to increase communication effectiveness (Swain, 1984) and fluency (Dörnyei&Thurrell's, 1991). The ways are described as increasing communication performance by employment of effective method to make listener able to identify the intended message (Yule and Tarone, 1990) or manipulation of insufficient competence (Paribakht, 1986; Dörnyei&Thurrell, 1991). Preventing from too broad interpretation of the concept, Brown (2007) made a boundary of strategic competence definition by setting a limitation of the theory coverage which focuses on counteractin lacks of competences to meet communicative goals.

The strategic competence includes “verbal and non-verbal communication strategies” (Canalé& Swain, 1980) in which every speaker might select consciously and employ different strategies to each other due to individual communication goals (Chamot, 2005). Furthermore, in second language learning scope, the “communication strategies” refer to learners’ effort to express meaning or deliver messages to others productively (Brown, 2007). The strategies are valuable means for learners to achieve a degree of communicativeness beyond their current linguistic knowledge by compensating for unexpected communication impasses (Thornbury, 2005).

Motivated by the promising option of solution to increase learners’ speaking ability and considering the influential aspects of communication strategies practice, this research is focused on investigating how Indonesian learners’ engage with communication strategies during their classroom interaction. The interest will not be limited to identification of kinds of communication strategy, but it will continue to discover the frequency of every strategy usage which indicates the pattern of learners’ choices. Moreover, considering the influence of foreign language proficiency and foreign culture knowledge in communication, the investigation will cover also learners’ CC and WTC. The inquiry will not be limited to survey result, but expanding to examine possibility of association among language proficiency, CC, WTC and communication strategies use. In short, Canalé& Swain’s (1980) communicative competence would be used as the basis of studies related to communication strategies used by learners and cultural aspects in terms of learners’ intercultural communicative competence as well as willingness to communicate.

Research Questions

Considering the background of the problem and the purposes of the research, the research problems are:

1. What are communication strategies used by learners?
2. How does learners’ communicative competence take place?

Literature Review

Communicative Competence

Communicative competence refers to the ability to use language in interaction to understand messages and make ourselves understood in turn (Thornbury, 2005). According to Canale& Swain (1980) communicative competence comprises four components: grammatical competence, discourse competence, sociolinguistic competence, and strategic competence, which reflects the use of the linguistic system and the functional aspects of communication respectively. Linguistics and sociolinguistics competence are used of the linguistic system, i.e. grammar, vocabulary; whereas discourse and strategic competences are those for use of the functional aspect of communication. Brown (1994) defines strategic competence is the way learners manipulate language to meet communicative goals.

For the need of communication, strategic competence and communication strategies are interrelated. Flor (2008) defines strategic competence concerns with the knowledge of communication strategies and how to use them. According to Flor (2008) strategic competence is the knowledge of how to use communication strategies to handle hindrances in communication. In Flor's opinion (2008) the speakers of English need to have the knowledge on how to use communication. Brown (1994) adds by using communication strategies, the speakers can get across the communicative goals to the interlocutors successfully.

Communication Strategies

To define a clear concept of communication strategies, this part presents definitions from scholars. Bialystok (2010) defines communication strategy as an individual's attempt to find ways to fill the gap between their communication effort and immediately available linguistic resources. Communication strategies indicate endeavours made by a speaker to compensate their inadequate linguistic knowledge. Tarone (1983) defines communications strategies as mutual attempts of two interlocutors to agree on a meaning in situations where requisite meaning structures do not seem to be shared. In addition, Dornyei (1995) views communication strategies as the ways a person employs to cope with problems and difficulties in oral communication such. According to Faerch & Kasper (1983) communication strategies as the potentially conscious plans for solving what an individual presents itself as a problem in reaching a particular communicative goal. Corder (1981) defines communication strategies as systematic techniques employed by a speaker to express his meaning when faced with some difficulties. According to O'Malley & Chamot (1990) communication strategies can also be used to negotiate meaning between speakers and interlocutors.

To say in other words, communication strategies (1) helps effective communication (Canale, 1983), (2) is able to negotiate meaning between speakers and interlocutors (O'Malley & Chamot, 1990), (3) cope with difficulties when communicating in target language (Dornyei, 1995), (4) help solve problem in reaching a particular communicative goal (Faerch & Kasper, 1983), and (5) keep the conversation doing (Nakatani, 2006). This study uses definition of Dornyei (1995) of which the elaboration on the communication strategies will be developed.

Communication Strategies

When communication strategies occur, there are two types of strategies used by interlocutors, avoidance strategies and achievement strategies (Dornyei, 1995). Students who are still immature of English will use avoidance to reduce their communication goal. The students tend to speak on the safe side. Therefore, the students are called non-risk takers (Dornyei, 1995; Nakatani, 2006; Faerch & Casper, 1983). Dornyei (1995) defines two strategies in these respects: (1) Topic Avoidance: Learners try not to talk about the concepts which they find it difficult to express, and (2) Message abandonment: leaving the message unfinished due to lack of a structural or linguistic item.

Dornyei (1995) and Nakatani (2006) to fill their gaps in communication, the learners of L2 communicate using strategies and meaning negotiation. There are 11 strategies of communication as appears in table 1. Dornyei (1995) and Nakatani (2006) list the avoidance strategies include: (1) approximation, (2) circumlocution, (3) word coinage, (4) foreignizing, (5) borrowing, (6) appeal for help, (7) code switching, (8) literal translation, (9) use of fillers or hesitation devices, (10) all purposes-word, and (11) non-verbal strategies.

Table 1: Strategies of communication by students by Dornyei (1995) & Nakatani (2006)

Strategies of CS	Definition
1. Approximation:	Using an alternative expression which may not express exactly what it means. e.g. 'stool' for 'chair'; 'bird' for 'owl'; 'ship' for 'sail'.
2. Circumlocution/paraphrase:	Describing or explaining the meaning, or the function of the target expression. e.g. a type of vehicle, something we use to....., it has four legs,.....
3. Word coinage:	Creating an L2 word thinking that it might work. e.g. 'fish zoo' for 'aquarium'
4. Foreignizing:	Trying out an L1 word but adjusting it slightly phonologically or morphologically. In an Indonesian study, a learner does not know the word 'tap' in English, he uses the L1 word 'kran' but with L2 pronunciation, so he says 'kren'.
5. Borrowing:	Using a word from other languages. For example, when a German native speaker uses a word or an expression which is not part of his/her L1 or L2. While him/she is communication with a native English speaker. Let us say an Arabic word or French.
6. Appeal for help:	It means asking the interlocutor for help. E.g. what does it mean in English? Was its... auf English?
7. Code switching:	Refers to the use or the insertion of a language item other than the language used in the discourse.
8. Literal translation:	It refers to word-for-word translation from the native language to the target language. e.g. 'Electrical stairs' for 'escalator'.
9. Use of fillers/hesitation devices:	a learner may use filling words to fill a pause and to gain time to think. e.g. well, as a matter of fact, actually, as you know, sort of, um, er, em, as you see, I think
10. All purpose words:	Words used to fill in the gap, These words are over used. e. g. stuff, thing, make, do..
11. Non-verbal strategies:	The use of non-linguistic resources such as mime, gestures, facial expressions, and sound imitation to help the learner/speaker express the meaning. E.g. moving hands to explain the meaning of flying.

In addition, Nakatani (2006) and Dornyei (1995) define 6 strategies of negotiation as in table 2. The strategies include: (1) asking for help, (2) asking for repetition, (3) asking for clarification, (4) asking for confirmation, (5) comprehension check, and (6) guessing.

Table 2: Negotiation strategies (Nakatani, 2006) & Dornyei (1995)

Negotiation strategies	Definition
1. Appeal for help:	Trying to elicit help from your partner by asking an explicit question to fill the information gap. Examples: What do you call it? What is it called? How do you spell it?
2. Asking for repetition:	Requesting repetition when not hearing or misunderstanding something properly. Examples: Pardon? Beg your pardon? What? Can you say it again, please?
3. Asking for clarification:	Requesting explanation of an unfamiliar meaning structure. Examples: What do you mean? You saw what?
4. Asking for confirmation/ Confirmation request:	Requesting confirmation that one heard or understood something correctly. It might be by asking full questions. Examples: You mean....? You said...? Do you mean that...?
5. Comprehension check:	Asking questions to check that the interlocutor or partner is following you. Examples: Are you following me? You know what I mean? Have you got my point?
6. Guessing:	It involves real indecision and uncertainty. Example: Is it a sink? Is it Newcastle club?

Communication Strategies Used by Learners

Not only foreign language learner, but also native speakers of a language have ever had problems to find the appropriate word or sentences to express the message in a communication event. Delivering meaning to interlocutor may need steps to make the delivery understandable and effective. The efforts to send the message effectively are known as “communication strategies” (Littlemore, 2003).

Therefore, strategic competence is relevant to both first language and second language. It involves strategies to be used when learners wish to convey messages but their linguistic resources do not allow them to express successfully. Furthermore, adult learners might use the same communication strategies in second language as in first language: even they are transferable from first language to the second language (Paribakht, 1985; Bongaerts&Poulisse, 1989).

Although CSs are very important in language learning, but CS research does not lack controversies. So far, there is no universally accepted definition of CSs because different

researcher might propose different definition of CSs based on individual perceptions and believed in each context of the research. Generally, CSs have been described as “all attempts to manipulate a limited linguistic system in order to promote communication” (Bialystok, 1983:102); “verbal and non-verbal strategies that may be called into action to compensate for breakdowns in communication due to limited conditions in actual communication or to insufficient competence in one or more of the other areas of communicative competence, and to enhance the effectiveness of communication” (Canale, 1983:10); “a subset of language learning strategies, focusing on approaches for conveying meaningful information that is new to the recipient (Cohen, 1996); “ways of achieving communication by using language in the most effective way” (Bygate, 2000:115); “tactics taken by second language learners to solve oral communication problems” (Lam, 2006:142); “strategies that learners employ when their communicative competence in the language being learned is insufficient which include making learners themselves understood in the second language and having others help them understand” (William, 2006:2).

The characteristics of communication strategies can be derived by exploring how the notion was developed. Dörnyei&Thurrell (1991) supported Canale& Swain (1980) in developing the theory who mentioned that CSs referred to solving communication problems which are due to insufficiency of communicative competence aspects. Specifically, Dörnyei&Thurrell (1991) mentioned that communication strategies are means to achieve communication goal by applying a plan to communicate strategically.

Speech Production and Language Proficiency in Communication Strategies Perspective

Naturally speaking as a mean of interaction of people in a linguistic community (Akanbi, et. al., 2020) comes before building a written form of language (Willis, 2015) which both social practice and cognitive process are included in (Widodo, 2015a). As kinds of oral language skills, speaking and listening demand plentiful “mental process” which is in contact with “working memory” that developed learners’ experience in socialization process with the surrounding society (Goh, 2014; Willis 2015). The mental and physical processes are mutually interrelated that cover conceptualization, formulation, and articulation which are resulting speech production (Levelt&Levelt et al., 1989; 1999, as cited in Goh, 2014). It is believed that pre-task planning is a valuable means to assist learners to overcome problems of limited resources which in turn it will increase performance of the task (Guará-Tavares, 2016) by triggering a range of strategic language behaviour (Ortega, 2005). Furthermore, it is regarded as a problem solving activity (Ellis, 2005).

The definition is partly intersected with Poulisse’s (1997) definition, which sees CS as “the expression of an alternative speech plan” when the original plan failed to be codable. The production of speech in a communication activity should be compared to a kind of quality statement to meet acceptable value which refers to language proficiency. As it was cited by Renandya (2018), Richards (2018) stated that language proficiency refers to one’s ability to use language for a variety of communicative purposes.

Knight (1992) explained in more detail depiction on how to evaluate in speaking test. The grammar is evaluated in terms of the usage range and accuracy. The concept of fluency was in accordance with Schmidt (1992) which was cited by Pakula (2019) who analyzed it quantitatively as a time-based phenomenon with a focus on automatization, speech rate and length of pauses.

It is a significant note that speaking is not a simple activity for foreign language learners when they are required to express both content knowledge and linguistic properties in such acceptable way in accordance with the language's social-cultural system (Bern, 1990). The challenge to speak is increasing since these aspects namely lexico grammar, cognitive processes, speaking anxiety, and lack of perceived speaking practices may cause learners difficult to engage to speaking tasks (Gan, 2013). Furthermore, in some cases, speaking anxiety emerged from a peer negative evaluation of their speaking activity, and this was considered as embarrassment (Widodo, 2015b). Another factor influencing speaking activity is "willingness to communicate" (WTC) in foreign language (Cao, 2011) which particularly rooted from the problems of self-confidence, topic and task type, and lack of language proficiency which may obstruct students from active participation in speaking class and, in turn, may affect their speaking fluency.

Related to culture as the background of language, further explanation about culture is given by Brown (2007) who states that culture is a way of life, mental programs (Hofstede, et. al., 2010) which include patterns of thinking, feeling and potential acting that were learned throughout the person's lifetime, so it may influence the member of the culture to think, feel and relate to each other. Meanwhile, culture is an integral part of the interaction between language and thought (Brown, 2007: 210).

People are demonstrating intercultural communication (Bennet, 1998; Pinto, 2000; Samovar, et. al., 2012) or cross-cultural communication (Angelelli, 2004; Warren, 2015). Many CC research revealed how it was developed and how it influences. ICC does not have any relevance with the use of technology (Vuksanovic, 2018). It refers to less influence of technology to its development. However, computer-mediated communities provided the learners a way to co-construct their intercultural knowledge, attitude and discovery (Chen, 2017). Different contexts of those researches may cause different results. The immersion programs had been reported as a method to develop CC (Douglas & Rosvold, 2018; Ngai & Janusch, 2015). The purpose of the program was to familiarize the culture and the norms of the target language. The researches by Douglas & Rosvold (2018) and Arasaratnam & Banerjee (2011) found that ethnocentrism was possible to hinder the CC development because it may cause cultural misunderstanding which in turn it will cause miscommunication among the speakers. On the other hand, the CC development brought positive correlation with motivation, intercultural knowledge, second language attitude, and intercultural discovery (Arasaratnam & Banerjee, 2011; Chen, 2017; Vuksanovic, 2018). Most of all, Aguilar (2011) had reminded that CC acquisition was a lifelong learning activity and it was a never completed process since culture was also learned lifelong too.

The choice of communication strategies may be different between a person to another because it is influenced by individual target of the communication (Chamot, 2005), although the individual differences may change “from time to time and from situation to situation” (Dörnyei, 2010:252). This fact attracts curiosity to reveal any factors that are likely to influence the choice. A possible factor that is predicted to induce is the factor of WTC. The motive of the prediction refers back to the concept of communication strategy that the strategies are employed only in a condition where “communication problems” happen due to inadequate competence. It implies speaker’s willingness to transfer message but “communication problems” occur.

The use of second or foreign language and the interaction using the language which is being learned are widely recognized as prerequisites for successful L2 acquisition (Gass & Mackey, 2015). But the absence of learners’ desire to engage in language production makes either the use of the language or the interaction hardly to occur. The desire is then called as WTC. Fostering learners’ WTC is therefore now a fundamental goal of second language education worldwide (Riasati, 2012). MacIntyre (2003) explained that it is an “overwhelming communication personality construct” which enters every facet of an individual’s life and strongly influence to the social, educational, and organizational achievements of the individual’.

Learners’ WTC could vary depending on the situation where the learners were engaged in a communication task (Cao & Philp, 2006; Noels, 2001). Factors that are possible to influence the WTC are to the interlocutor(s), topic, and conversational context, among other potential situational variables’ (Kang, 2005). The other factors which are called as situational variables are anxiety and perceived competence (MacIntyre, Babin, Clément, 1999), communication confidence (Peng and Woodrow, 2010), classroom conditions, group cohesiveness and topic relevance (Aubrey, 2011). Particular, “anxiety” appears to play a major role as it causes learners to avoid or reduce communication (Alemi, et. al., 2011). Another major reason of low participation in second language classroom is a “lack of self-confidence” (MacIntyre, et. al., 2003). In addition, Vongsila & Reinders (2016) reported teachers’ awareness on developing learners’ WTC and helping learners to identify a range of strategies they used in class.

Method

Research Design

Considering the research problem and objectives, this research is a qualitative phenomenology in nature in which the central element of the study is a search to understand how people meet the phenomenon and recognize their feeling and experience related to the phenomenon from their perspective respectively (Johnson & Chistensen, 2014). This study investigated characteristics of communication strategies used by the speakers applied in performing speaking tasks in English class.

Subject of Research

The subjects of the study were not purposively selected although the respondents must fulfil specified criteria to meet the aim. The subjects of this study are students of non-English Department of tertiary level education institutions in Surabaya, specifically they are students of marine electrical engineering study program. Criteria in choosing the subject of research are that they are non-English students who learn English as a compulsory subject. The number of participant in this research is 25 of 56 students population. The respondents are randomly selected without considering the gender and proficiency at preliminary stage. The age ranged from 20 to 23 years old to represent adult learners of English.

Data Collection and Research Instrument

Two techniques of data collection were employed, namely observation and interview. The observations were taken to collect data of the communication strategies use in respondents' speeches. The speeches were also recorded and transcribed to support findings gathered in the form of observation notes. The observation technique was operated to collect data of respondents' intercultural attitude and skills, and willingness to communicate too. Following the observation, interview was managed to dig out background and reasons behind the action. Those two techniques utilized in collecting data in this study were already validated by two validators who are two lecturers teaching in Electronics Engineering Polytechnic of Surabaya and Sepuluh Nopember Institute of Technology.

Interviews were also conducted to gain data related to speakers' feeling and experience when facing and solving communication problems, their intercultural communication strategies and willingness to communicate. Interview was managed in communication strategy research since selection of strategies was individual in nature, that each speaker might choose particular communication strategies. In searching respondents' attitude, knowledge and skills as elements of intercultural communicative competence, this method of data collection was applied to gather data of their cultural awareness. On the other hand, in research of learners' willingness to communicate this technique was valuable to dig out reasons why some speakers had willingness to participate in a discussion while the others had none. As one of data collection methods, interview allowed the researcher to understand a phenomenon through exploration process of initial suspicions and development of preliminary theories (Trochim & Donnelly, 2008).

Data Analysis

There will be two steps of data analysis. The first one is analysing the result of observation, describing of the actual use of communication strategies in delivering opinions and their willingness to communicate in English during the task performances. The result specified an indication of kinds of strategies use and to postulate strategy use in relation to the language proficiency, the intercultural communicative competence, and the willingness to communicate factors. The second one was that comparing the results of observation and interview with the working framework to find out the finding in the theory in general.

Research Findings and Discussion

Communication Strategies Used by Learners in Planned Speeches

Generally, there were four prominent strategies which were used by the respondents, namely self-repetition, code-switching, “self-repair” and use of fillers strategies. The first two strategies were employed by ten respondents, the third one was used by nine respondents and the last one employed by eight respondents. The other strategies were used by one or two speakers each. “Self-repetition” and “code switching” strategies became the most popular strategies which were used by the respondents. Each strategy was used by 10 of 25 respondents who employed it in their speech. The table 3 shows the distribution of communication strategies used by speakers.

Table 3: Communication Strategies Use in Planned Speech

No.	Communication Strategy	Number of Speaker
1.	Code switching	11
2.	Self-repetition	10
3.	Self-repair	9
4.	Use a filler	8
5.	Omission	3
6.	Direct appeal for help	2
7.	Retrieval	2
8.	Approximation	2
9.	Use of all purposes words	1
10.	Foreignizing	1
11.	Circumlocution	1
12.	Message abandonment	1
13.	Message replacement	1

Source: Students’ presentation on proposal summary and/or telling experience during internship

The number of user of code-switching is the highest which made the strategy the most popular to employ in this study in term of user. The occurrence of this strategy found in 11 respondents. The second position is self-repetition strategy which was used by 10 respondents. The third position is self-repair strategy which was utilized by 9 respondents. And the fourth one is “use of filler” strategy which was used by 8 respondents. The rest was employed by not more than three respondents respectively. In conclusion, the first four strategies can be regarded as the dominant strategies, and the others are less dominant ones.

Communication Strategies Used by Learners in Unplanned Speeches

Observation discovered specific characteristics distinguishing them from what were found in planned speeches. Most speakers spoke in a relatively slower speed and use a kind of fillers “em” to gain time before they continue speaking. Only seven types of communication

strategy were employed during performing the tasks. The table 4 shows the distribution of communication strategies used by speakers.

Table 4: Communication strategies use in unplanned speeches

No.	Communication Strategy	Number of Speaker
1.	Self-repair	13
2.	Self-repetition	13
3.	Use a filler	12
4.	Code switching	6
5.	Omission	3
6.	Circumlocution	2
7.	Retrieval	2

Source: Students' spontaneous speeches speaking tasks to answer questions directly after they were launched were developed in which the questions were given in oral and written forms

Speakers' speech during performing these tasks were strongly characterized by silence between points to share, a kind of hesitation markers, although only some of them who used fillers like "e" and "yes" which were meaningless. They preferred to stop for a while rather than maintaining the speed of speaking. The break happened randomly, not only on the transition of an idea to another, but also between words. So, the delivery of speech took a long time because speakers tended to gain time before speaking. This phenomenon was shown by respondent #22 who spoke 146 words in 3.32 minutes; it means that he produced about 44 words in a minute. On the other hand, respondent #16 produced 163 words in 2.15 minutes or about 76 words per minute.

A careful observation on respondents' speeches must be taken to avoid misunderstanding in identification of communication strategies. A speaker seemed to practice "omission" strategy both in planned and unplanned speeches which it was defined as a strategy when a speaker left a gap when he was not knowing a word and carrying on as if it had been said. But in fact, this was a kind of speaking style which was very common in spoken language.

Communication Strategies Used by Learners in Conversations

Different from previous tasks, these tasks were used to draw speakers' use of communication strategies in a conversation among respondents. The tasks were characterized by spontaneous speeches and direct interaction which involved not only speaking task but also listening task in certain context.

From the observation, there were important findings to present in this part. Almost all speakers spoke in "normal" speed with a lot of employment of special words and expressions that were typically used among friends or close friends like greetings, "Ok... Ok", "bro", and "guys". In performing this task, respondent # 15 produced 90 words per minute. There were seven communication strategies to employ during performing the tasks. There were students who spoke in slower speeds when performing the planned tasks, just like the way they speak

in performing unplanned speech. Overall, the strategies to use were “self-repetition”, “self-repair”, “foreignizing”, “code switching”, “use of fillers”, “approximation”, non-verbal, and message abandonment strategies.

To give clearer picture about communication strategies which were used in conversation, the following table informs the kinds of strategy and the number of speakers who used the strategies respectively. See table 5.

Table 5: Communication strategies use in conversation

No.	Communication Strategy	Number of Speaker
1.	Self-repetition	14
2.	Use a filler	12
3.	Code Switching	10
4.	Self-repair	8
5.	Approximation	1
6.	Non-verbal	1
7.	Message abandonment	1
8.	Foreignizing	1

Source: Student conversation

Additionally, there was not any sign to stop speaking when there was indication of problem arising. The expressions which were employed as fillers did not show any hesitancy, so they did not signify any hesitation markers. The words like “yes”, and “er” or “em” were exploited to keep oral interaction.

Learners’ Perception on Planned Communication Strategies to apply

Following the same procedure, all answers of the respondents indicated particular communication strategies which were consciously selected. The selection of communication strategy to solve communication problem was individual in nature although it did not mean that a respondent only picked a strategy. There were several respondents signalled to use two strategies. Since the analysis would be on individual basis, so it was important to reflects how respondents conceived themselves in dealing with communication problems respectively. See table 6.

Table 6: Learners’ Perception on Planned Communication Strategies to Apply

Occurrence Indicator	Communication Strategy	Number of Respondents
Using synonymous words	Negotiation for meaning	16
Using gesture	Non verbal	3
Using familiar words only, changing word	Message reduction and alteration	8
Using different language, stop speaking	Message abandonment	2
Thinking of a sentence in English	Attempt to think in English	1

Source: Student conversation

The result shows us that “negotiation for meaning” strategy became the one which often occurred in the planning stage that was projected to overcome communication problems if they happened in performing speaking tasks. The strategy would be implemented by using synonym of the words or expressions to substitute the intended words which were unable to be recalled. The synonymous words were chosen to maintain the message to deliver. Nevertheless, “message reduction and alteration”, “non-verbal”, “message abandonment”, and “attempt to think in English” strategies had been mentioned too although they were not as popular as “negotiation for meaning” strategy. The table below represents ranking of tendency of conscious or planned strategies which were proposed by the respondents.

Learners’ Intercultural Competence

The essays which were written during the writing tasks were rich of data on how a respondent saw and valued his own language and culture followed by his outlook on other language and culture. The essay was read carefully to find valuable expressions presenting respondent’s cultural competence. The expressions, then, were extracted to get the theme raised by the writer which in turn all themes were classified into groups representing each component of ICC. On the other hand, in reading tasks, respondents were required to answer particularly designed questions to elicit learners’ ICC. A related reading text was assigned to them before answering comprehension questions and those specifically intended questions in enrichment section. So, an item of ICC component had been assessed, at least, by two instruments.

Conclusion and Implication

In summary, communication strategies employed by respondents in many different conditions considered speech production which gradually followed conceptualization step, formulation step, and articulation step. Tasks for planned speeches put emphasize on conceptualization step which allowed respondents to gather and select ideas or information before performing the tasks. One for unplanned speeches which did not give adequate time of preparation depended so much on respondents’ prior knowledge about subject to speak. Without neglecting the conceptualization step which happened almost immediately, the performance of these tasks were determined by formulation process of respondents. Meanwhile, the conversation tasks facilitated respondents’ competence to get through socialization process with the surrounding society. Based on the results of observation, it is found that there are 14 communication strategies of taxonomy used by respondents, two strategies are used by 10 respondents each, namely self-repetition and code switching strategies. Meanwhile, the most frequently used strategy is use of filler which is employed only by 8 respondents. Based on the results of data analysis, it is found that some communication strategies are employed more frequently than those of the other strategies which lay on the employment of “use of all purposes words” and “foreign zing” strategies that are found in the current study only. Furthermore, this research finds that “self-repetition” strategy is the most popular strategy to use.

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